

eScience Center Fellowship Programme 2024: Application Form

December 2023

REGISTRATION FORM (BASIC DATA)

This document contains explanatory text in italics. Please remove this text before submission.

1a. Details of the fellowship applicant

Surname, first name, title(s)	
Email address	
Institute	
Department	
Section	
Address	
Postcode	
City	
Tel	

1b. What is your current occupation / career stage?

- PhD candidate
- Postdoctoral researcher
- Assistant professor
- Associate professor
- Professor
- Data steward
- Research software engineer
- Other, namely:

2a. Title of your proposed fellowship plan

A short and specific title that describes the activities carried out in the plan.

2b. Summary for the eScience Center website (max 150 words)

Please provide a non-expert summary of the plan for use on the eScience Center website and other media.

Please take into account that the proposal summary provided and the summary for non-experts, may be used for publication purposes, should your application be awarded, and that it will be subject to editing.

2c. In which of the four categories below does your project fit most closely?

Please rank the four disciplines in order of relevance to your project (1: most closely related to your project, 4: least related to your project). This will be used to partner you with the most relevant point of contact at the eScience Center.

Discipline	Rank
Environment and sustainability	
Natural sciences and engineering	
Life sciences	
Social sciences and humanities	

FELLOWSHIP PROJECT PLAN

3. Project plan

Please paste the text of your project plan here. The text and illustrations should facilitate easy reading and should be self-contained. The plan should be a proposal for a project that improves the state of research software (max 1500 words including references). This must include:

1. A reflection on the awareness and/or use of research software in the academic community, discipline, or field of the applicant.
2. A description of the applicant's objectives related to improving research software.
3. A description of any activities that will be undertaken to achieve the applicant's objectives.
4. A justification of why the applicant is well situated to execute the planned activities, and act as an ambassador for research software.

4. Fellowship timeline

Please provide a realistic timeline, running between June 2024 and end of May 2025, that demonstrates when you will plan and undertake the activities that are part of your project plan. The timeline may need to be adjusted during the project; this will always happen in consultation between the Fellow and the eScience Center.

5. Fellowship budget specification

Please paste a budget that specifies how your personal fellowship budget will be used below. The budget should outline how the personal budget of **€2,000 + 40 hours of eScience Center expertise** ("in-kind support") will be used: the plan should outline the expenses and consumables the budget will cover in the form of declared costs. In addition, the plan should outline how eScience Center employee time is expected to be used. It should be clear from the plan that these hours are directly relevant to the proposed activities. Hours can be used at different times throughout the year, or all at once, for several eScience Center employees simultaneously.

ADMINISTRATIVE DETAILS

6. Statements by the applicant

The eScience Center strictly applies the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the EU regulation aimed at strengthening data protection for all individuals within the EU (see www.eugdpr.org). In the Netherlands the regulation is implemented as the 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG)'. Applicants must strictly apply these rules and regulations, as well as the principles, in as much as these are applicable to the proposed work.

Applicants are asked to endorse and follow the Netherlands eScience Center Rules towards Publishing, Licensing, and Intellectual Property (available at www.esciencecenter.nl). For alternative IP agreements, contact the eScience Center before proposal submission.

- I endorse and follow the rules and regulations as laid out in the 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG), as well as the underlying principles (GDPR).
- I endorse and follow the eScience Center Rules towards Publishing, Licensing, and IP. **If 'NO', then please justify, and contact the eScience Center before submitting the application.**
- I have completed this form truthfully.

Name:

Place:

Date:

To submit your application, send the completed form to fellowship@esciencecenter.nl. The deadline for application is 08 April, 2024, 14:00 CET.

Turn to the next page for an optional section.

OTHER INFORMATION (OPTIONAL)

7. A little more about you

The following section is **optional and will not affect your application**. Only share this information if you wish to share it. At the eScience Center, we are interested in the backgrounds of our project partners and future fellows. Therefore, we have a few questions about you.

7a. Which of the following disciplines are relevant to the research / work you do on a daily basis?

- Agricultural or Environmental Sciences
- Biomedical or Health Sciences
- Chemistry
- Civil, Mechanical, Chemical, or Nuclear Engineering
- Computer Science or Electrical Engineering
- Earth Sciences
- Economics or Business
- Genetics, Genomics, or Bioinformatics
- High Performance Computing
- Humanities
- Library and Information Sciences
- Life Sciences
- Mathematics or Statistics
- Medicine
- Organismal Biology
- Physical Sciences
- Planetary Sciences
- Psychology or Neuroscience
- Social Sciences
- Space Sciences
- Research Support

7b. What gender do you identify as?

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

7c. In which country did you complete the majority of your education?

7d. What is your nationality?

7e. Your GitHub, Twitter, and / or LinkedIn accounts: